

SELF-AWARENESS IN STUDENTS' ACTIVITIES

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Annotation: The purpose of this work is to indicate the role of self-awareness in the processes of learning and upbringing. In general, it is believed that every person is naturally capable of a certain direction. If a person works systematically on themselves, they can become an outstanding person. Self-awareness plays a significant role in the formation of a person's personality. It is challenging to control one's behavior and the consequences of their actions objectively.

It is even more difficult to objectively assess one's place in society and one's capabilities, as one's psychophysiological potential is largely determined by one's innate genetic traits, the type of higher nervous activity, and the emotional and volitional sphere.

The purpose of this work is to indicate the role of self-awareness in the processes of learning and upbringing. In general, it is believed that every person is naturally capable of a certain direction. If a person works systematically on themselves, they can become an outstanding person. Self-awareness plays a significant role in the formation of a person's personality. It is challenging to control one's behavior and the consequences of their actions objectively.

However, systematic and rigorous self-analysis is necessary, as it allows individuals to focus on their spiritual and moral development. Where does self-awareness begin? Where are its boundaries? In what connections does it appear? How to develop this unique human "self", which branches out into such complex formations as self-discipline, independence, self-love, self-esteem, self-control, self-development, self-education, self-improvement? Psychologists note that self-awareness develops gradually and, most likely, begins with the definition of one's own body. Then the child begins to be aware of himself in the system of various social dependencies, rights and obligations, norms and requirements. Self-awareness is the awareness of oneself, one's physical strength and mental abilities, one's actions and motives, one's relationship to the outside world, other people, and oneself.

Self-knowledge has a hierarchy of manifestations, from the lowest level of well-being through self-knowledge to the highest level of self-attitude, which is objectified in self-control and self-regulation of one's behavior [1]. The student's self-awareness is the awareness of their motives, goals, and learning techniques, as well as the awareness of themselves as a subject of learning activity who

organizes, guides, and controls the learning process. According to B.G. Ananyev, the student's self-awareness is the core of the student's activity.

The awakening and strengthening of interest in one's own personality is essential for the purposefulness of self-education and self-improvement. A student's self-awareness is formed on the basis of expanding their knowledge about the qualities they need as future citizens and specialists, as well as their adequate self-assessment of their level of development. This is facilitated by introducing the student to the patterns of personality formation, developing their ability to analyze their activities, and self-characterize themselves (their strengths and weaknesses). The most typical shortcomings of a student's self-awareness are subjectivity, bias, condescension, and insufficient self-criticism.

This is why some students, for example, lack a sufficiently high level of identification between their current academic activities and their future professional activities, and evaluate academic subjects based on a number of secondary criteria. There are different levels of understanding of higher education among students.

1. There is a lack of understanding of the relationship between academic subjects. Each academic subject is viewed in isolation.

2. Students establish basic logical connections between subjects. However, they do not reflect the content of professional activity, but rather indicate that the student is beginning to understand the diversity (multiplicity) of scientific approaches to the phenomena of everyday life. In the student's mind, there is a return from the division of the world into a number of independent areas of knowledge to an objective unity. Students begin to understand that the division of scientific disciplines is relative.

1. In the students' minds, there is an expansion of the connections between the subjects they are studying and their future professional activities, both directly visible and indirect. Based on the study of individual disciplines, more general subjects are identified that are significantly related to the structure of professional activities. At this level, students' consciousness and self-awareness are characterized by the presence of cross-subject connections, which not only provide access to the structure and content of future professional activities, but also ensure a direct link between activities and the development of professional qualities.

The level of full awareness of the connection between the content of the educational process and professional activities in their dynamic context. Thus, if each individual follows the rules we have mentioned above, they can achieve a

lot. However, this requires hard work, attention, and, of course, self-awareness. As we have already discussed, self-awareness requires systematic and planned work based on a thorough self-improvement program.

List of references

1. Авдеева Н.Н. Привязанность ребенка к матери и образ себя в раннем детстве // Вопросы психологии. - № 4. - 1997. - с. 25 - 30.
2. Алексеев В.А. Развитие самосознания на рубеже подросткового и юношеского возрастов: Автореф. дисс. канд. психол. наук. - М., 1985. - 20 с.
3. Ананьев Б.Г. Избранные психологические труды - М.: Педагогика, т. 2, 1980. - 286 с.
4. Андреева Т.М. Социальная психология. - М.: Аспект-пресс, 1998. - 373 с.
5. Бернс Р. Развитие "Я-концепции" и воспитание. - М.: Просвещение, 1986. - 226 с.
6. Бондаревская Е.В. Ценностные основания личностно ориентированного воспитания // Педагогика. - №4. - 1995. - с. 29 - 36.

